

Impacts of alien invasive pines on lizard diversity.

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Aim

Globally, little is known about the mechanisms underlying the impacts of alien invasive plants on lizard communities. This study aims to assess the impacts of invasive pine (*Pinus radiata*) on lizard species diversity along an invasion gradient by measuring:

- Lizard species richness & evenness,
- Habitat thermal quality,
- Prey quantity & quality.

Figure 1. Theoretical expectations for the relationships between species richness/abundance & habitat type. A: lizard diversity is expected to increase with habitat complexity. B: at intermediate stages of invasion, lizard diversity & abundance may peak (red) or decline linearly (blue).

Methods

3 locations within the Western Cape Province, South Africa, Nov 2012 – April 2013

Lizards: Y-pitfall arrays, active searching, coverboards.

Insects: Pitfall cups, bush beating, Berlese Tullgren funnel extractions.

Thermal habitat: Lizard copper models, vegetation variables, sun & shade, weather station.

Figure 2. (A) Invasion gradient, (B) sampling design for each replicate, 3 replicates/site within each (C) location.

Statistics:

Species accumulation curves, rank-abundance plots, Shannon-Wiener diversity index, Simpson evenness index, multivariate analyses (EstimateS, Primer & R 2.12.2).

So far...

Figure 3. A: Pitfall with fencing. B-E species caught: B: *Agama atra*; C: *Trachylepis capensis*; D: *Ouroborus cataphractus*; E: *Tetradactylus seps*.

Impact

By assessing the effects of habitat quality (thermal & prey availability) on lizard diversity along an invasion gradient, this study will provide essential data to inform decisions on lizard conservation and land management.